

Linguistic Diversity in Decline? A Data-intensive Study of Indian Book Production Trends (2016-2025) via ISBN Metadata

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Abstract

This paper examines trends in book and monographic publications in India during 2016-2025 using ISBN registration data from the Raja Rammohun Roy National Agency for ISBN under the Ministry of Education, Government of India. ISBN data were analysed to identify year-wise growth patterns, language-wise distribution of publications, linguistic diversity, and reader engagement. The data were processed using OpenRefine and then analysed with Python scripts, which were supported by Microsoft Excel.

The results show overall growth in ISBN registrations from 2016 to 2025. A temporary decline was observed during the COVID-19 pandemic. The results indicate a rapid and robust recovery following the pandemic; by 2022, total monographic production (282,834) had surpassed 2019 pre-pandemic levels (166,356) by approximately 70%, with continued exponential growth reaching 382,646 registrations in 2023. English dominates, accounting for nearly two-thirds of total ISBN registrations, followed by Hindi. Regional languages such as Tamil, Bengali, Marathi, and Malayalam exhibited steady growth. Linguistic diversity increased through 2022, then declined in subsequent years due to a concentration in dominant languages.

The study also highlighted new trends in e-book publishing from 2020 onwards which indicates a long-term digital transition. Analysis of Goodreads ratings shows that a large proportion of publications remain unrated. Conversely rated titles tend to cluster in mid-to-high rating categories that reflect uneven reader engagement.

Overall, the study shows national publishing trends and underscores the need to introduce targeted policies to support linguistic diversity and access to knowledge in India. These findings have importance for library Collection Development.

Keywords: ISBN; Book Publishing; Digital Publishing; Post-publication Popularity; Trends in Book Production

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1. Introduction

Libraries are closely connected with the book trade. Published books play an essential role in disseminating knowledge and cultural expression in a multilingual society like India. The Indian Constitution supports linguistic diversity by recognising 22 languages. This also reflects in the market dynamics and language policy. ISBN (International Standard Book Number) registration data provides important bibliographic information to analyze ongoing trends in monographic production across different languages.

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Though an ISBN contains significant information, libraries have given limited attention to the potential of ISBN data for revealing language-specific trends. Most existing research focuses on journal literature, citations, or library usage statistics, leaving book publishing unexplored. Language-wise trends in book publishing are significant for libraries, as they provide insights into Collection Development and multilingual access.

This study aims to fill this gap by analyzing ISBN registration data from 2016 to 2025 to examine growth patterns in book publishing and assess the linguistic diversity of publishing in India.

While this study primarily relies on official ISBN registration data to map trends in Indian monographic production, it incorporates reader engagement metrics from Goodreads as a vital secondary indicator. This secondary metric is used to validate the impact of the primary ISBN data, providing a qualitative layer of analysis that reflects how the increased book production correlates with actual reader interaction and reception.

2. Literature Review

Bibliometric and informetric approaches are used to analyse publication trends in library and information science. Usually, this type of study focuses on journal literature, citation analysis, authorship patterns and research impact indicators (Garfield, 1999; Sen, 2012). While these approaches provide valuable insights into scholarly publishing, book publishing—particularly in multilingual contexts—has received comparatively limited attention.

Several studies have examined publishing trends in India from a bibliometric perspective. Patra and Chand (2006) highlighted the importance of bibliometric techniques in analysing Indian publication output. Similarly, Bowker (2024) examined the global dynamics of scholarly communication with a particular focus on linguistic diversity and the role of language technologies that highlights how the dominance of English creates disparities for non-Anglophone scholars. It also discussed the potential and limitations of translation tools in supporting multilingualism within the academic publishing ecosystem, though without providing detailed empirical analyses of specific publication datasets.

Language diversity in publishing has been a recurring concern in both national and international studies. UNESCO (2016) highlighted the importance of linguistic diversity in publishing for cultural preservation with a warning against the global trend toward linguistic homogenization dominated by English.

Recent literature has increasingly focused on multilingual publishing and language policy in India. Chowdhary (2024) examined shifting patterns of multilingual publishing and also highlighted structural inequalities that favour English-language outputs despite the large readership base of Indian languages. Government initiatives and policy discussions reviewed by Reema (2024), have emphasized the promotion of regional and indigenous languages through publishing subsidies and translation programmes.

The transformation of the publishing industry which is heavily affected by digitalization has also been discussed. Market studies indicate rapid growth of e-books, audiobooks, and online distribution platforms. The British Council's India Literature and Publishing Sector Study documented these challenges faced by Indian publishers and highlighted the growth of digital formats in expanding readership.

Internationally, ISBN data has been recognised as a valuable data for analysing book production trends, language distribution, and diversity. Despite this there is not much study has been done on ISBN-based bibliometric studies in the Indian context. Existing research has

rarely worked on ISBN metadata to examine longitudinal trends, linguistic diversity, or the impact of external disruptions such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

In summary, some studies already been done to understand publishing trends, language policy, and digital transformation in India, there is a clear research gap in comprehensive, protracted analyses of book publishing using ISBN registration data. Moreover, language-wise trends, diversity measurement, and reader engagement indicators-such as online ratings-have not been adequately explored in a unified framework. The present study shows this gap by utilizing ISBN data from 2016 to 2025 to visualize year-wise growth, language distribution, diversity patterns, digital publishing trends, and reader engagement on the growing landscape of Indian book publishing.

3. Methodology

All the data were collected from www.isbn.gov.in and subsequently imported into OpenRefine. The data were analysed using Python scripts in combination with Microsoft Excel.

3.1 Data Collection

The study is based on ISBN registration data collected from the National ISBN Agency of India for the period 2016-2025. In the www.isbn.gov.in website, normally two type of search option is available, one is by type like ISBN Number/Series, Publishing Agency/Publisher, Author/Co-Author, Book Title, Year, Language, Product Form and the old portal have the option to search by Book Title, Email, Name of Publishing Agency/Publisher, Year, and ISBN Number. On the home page Live Registered Users, Received Applications, ISBN Issued, ISBN Allotted number is present.

The option to download the exact number is during a specific period is not available. If we use the link <https://isbn.gov.in/Home/SearchIsbnNew> then only the option to download all the books published during a period is available. Though, the information before 2016 is not available on the website, if we try to download from the website. More than 26 lakhs ISBN has been allotted during 2016 to 2025. Since this is a large number of data, it cannot be downloaded at once from their server; hence, it has been downloaded dividing it sometimes yearly and monthly based on the number of ISBN issued. Data format collected from the ISBN portal is attached in Annexure – I.

3.2 Data Extraction

After downloading all the data, it has been observed the there are some discrepancies in the data downloaded from the portal. These are:

1. From 2016 to 2020 and some data from 2021 does not have the publication date. Since the same has been downloaded after mentioning the specific dates, it has been assumed these are for these specific years only.
2. From 2021 to 2025 publication dates are available. Though we have downloaded the data month wise and sometime quarterly and half yearly basis, it has been observed that some of ISBN is for dates 08.01.1023 to 20.07.2823. This is not possible. We have imported all the data from 2016 to 2025 in OpenRefine and sorted it. Total ISBN issued was 26,27,017, the Publication Date column converted into Date following Edit Cells-Common Transforms - To date. Created a new column as Year using the GREL code “value [0,4]”. This code converted all the date into their respective years then the column converted into Text Facet and sorted as per year. The total number of ISBN issued between 2016 to 2025 is 25,60,729.

Year wise ISBN issued data has been collected by using text facet in OpenRefine. Year wise data has been exported as CSV, later by using a python code language wise break up has been obtained year-wise.

The top 10 languages are: English, Hindi, Tamil, Bengali, Marathi, Malayalam, Gujarati, Kanada, Urdu, Assamese. In Table 1, total number of publications of top 10 languages is mentioned and in Table 2, the exact number of ISBN issued from 2016 to 2025 is also listed.

Table 1: Number of publications of top 10 languages

Year	English	Hindi	Tamil	Bengali	Marathi	Malayalam	Gujarati	Kannada	Urdu	Assamese	Other Languages
2016	58070	13089	3767	1866	2934	1890	1281	1379	896	188	3382
2017	89849	20672	4098	3672	3979	2861	2277	2851	1102	646	6830
2018	54041	12765	2452	2854	3104	1775	1253	1235	756	321	4186
2019	105151	25902	4619	6045	5906	3882	3136	2117	1325	926	7207
2020	54909	12716	2238	3135	3007	2432	1361	1455	861	775	4037

Table 2: Number of ISBN issued from 2016 to 2025

Year	Total ISBN issued
2016	88763
2017	138858
2018	84791
2019	166356
2020	86959
2021	195243
2022	282834
2023	382646
2024	505073
2025	629206
Total	25, 60, 729

3.3 Product Diversity

Along with the language an important data can be collected which is Product form. The inclusion of product form data began in 2020. Around 123 different types of products were issued from 2016 to 2025. Some of important product forms are Book, Paperback/Softback, Hardback, e-book reader, Digital download and online etc. The top ten different type of product form issued during 2016 to 2025 is mentioned below along with the number of ISBN in Table 3.

Table 3: Total count of the top 10 product form

Product Form	Total Count
Book	1110972
Paperback / softback	482063
Hardback	153392
e-book reader	103368
Digital download and online	68901
Digital (delivered electronically)	41224
Board book	10213
Digital online	7712
Address book	5956
Digital Download	4901

3.4 Post-publication Popularity

Along with language wise data, information about review of all the issued ISBN retrieved using OpenRefine and Goodreads. A new column has been created a column has been created using the ISBN data downloaded from isbn.gov.in using the GREL code: `value.replace("-", "")`. This removed the – from the ISBN and transformed them into 13-digit numerical number. Then a new column has been created by fetching URLs, the GREL code: `"https://www.goodreads.com/book/review_counts.json?key=XXXXXX&isbn="+ value`. A new column created contains the average rating received from Goodreads. Then again, a new column based on the average rating column with GREL code: `value.parseJson().books[0].average_rating.toNumber()`, which contains the average rating in numerical value. Using text facet, the average rating has been sorted and total review received for 423,269.

3.5 e-book reader data

While the growth of e-books is widely recognized, the precise figures have remained undocumented. The total number of e-books published during 2016-2025 is mentioned in Table 4.

Table 4: e-books reader published during 2016-2025

Year	Total e-books Published
2016	15
2017	26
2018	38
2019	81
2020	4,171
2021	11,420
2022	11,788
2023	18,066
2024	23,023
2025	37,308
Total	105936

4. Data Analysis and Interpretation

4.1 Year-wise trends

The year-wise analysis shows a general upward trend in book and monographic publications between 2016 and 2025 (Figure 1) in India, with a sudden decline in 2020 corresponding to the COVID-19 pandemic and from 2021 data indicate a strong recovery and rapid growth in ISBN registrations. A critical inflection point is observed post-2021. While the pandemic caused an initial decline, the subsequent 'rapid recovery' represents a significant market expansion rather than a simple return to baseline. By 2023, the total registrations (382,646) were more than double the 2019 production volume (166,356). This suggests that the digital transition and shifting publication patterns during the pandemic years catalyzed an unprecedented increase in monographic output.

Figure 1: Year-wise Total ISBN published

The number of books and other printable media published in India has shown a consistent upward trend over the years. Total 88,763 ISBN issued in 2016 and the number increased in 2017 to 1,38,858. Later the number declined in 2018 to 84,791 but it again rose sharply to 1,66,356 in 2019. During 2020, despite disruptions due to the Covid-19, 86,959 ISBN was issued. A significant increase was again observed in 2021 with 1,95,243 publications, followed by a considerable rise to 2,82,834 in 2022. The growth accelerated continued in 2023 with 3,82,646 ISBN issued, and reached in 2024 to 5,05,073. By 2025, a total of 6,29,206 ISBN had been issued. Overall, between 2016 and 2025, a total of 25, 60, 729 ISBNs have been issued (Table 2).

4.2 Language-wise distribution

The language-wise analysis mentioned in Figure 2 shows dominance of English-language publications in India during the period 2016-2025. Total 1,659,194 ISBN registrations for English language, nearly 65% of the total ISBNs issued during the study period, clearly indicating dominant position in the Indian publishing.

Hindi appears as the second most prominent language, with 400,313 ISBNs, contributed around 16% of the total output. Together English and Hindi comprise more than four-fifths of all ISBN registrations. Among regional languages, Tamil (84,919) and Bengali (81,352) show nearly similar levels of publication results, come after Marathi (69,243) and Malayalam (54,780). Other Indian languages such as Gujarati (30,127), Kannada (27,361), Urdu (20,977), and Assamese (18,866) complete the top ten languages by total ISBN registrations during 2016-2025.

Overall, the language-wise distribution of ISBNs shows dominance of English in the Indian publishing sector, alongside moderate publication activity in Major Indian and regional languages.

Figure 2: Top 10 Languages by ISBN issued (2016-2025)

4.3 Major publication languages

In the year-wise distribution of major publishing languages from 2016 to 2025, a consistent dominance of English is demonstrated shown in Figure 3. A total of 58,079 ISBNs were issued in the English language in 2016, which increased to 89,858 in 2017. This was followed by fluctuations in 2018 (54,054) and 2020 (54,932). A continuous growth began in 2019 (105,225), and the numbers increased significantly after 2021, reaching 1,72,869 in 2022, 2,51,756 in 2023, and peaking at 4,22,513 by 2025.

Hindi maintained its position as the second most prominent publishing language during this period. The number of Hindi publications rose from 13,094 in 2016 to 20,674 in 2017, but declined in 2018 and 2020, before increasing from 31,926 in 2021 to 1,00,123 in 2025.

Among regional languages, comparable growth can be seen in Tamil and Bengali. Publications in the Tamil language increased from 3,767 in 2016 to 7,066 in 2021, showing growth to 19,279 in 2025. Bengali publications rose from 1,867 in 2016 to 7,311 in 2021, further to 20,228 in 2025.

Marathi and Malayalam also have shown growth over the 2016 to 2025 period. Publications in Marathi increased from 2,935 in 2016 to 13,656 in 2025, while Malayalam publications rose from 1,890 to 10,594 during the same period. Overall, the analysis indicates a significant expansion in the publishing of English alongside major Indian languages, particularly after 2021.

Figure 3: Year-wise distribution of Major Publishing Languages

4.4 Percentage share of major languages

The year-wise ISBN-based publication data reveals stability and moderate shifts in the linguistic formation of Indian publishing from 2016 to 2025, shown in Figure 4. Publication in the English language dominates the results, holding a 65.43% share in 2016, followed by a decline to 60.91% in 2021, and rising again to 67.15% in 2025.

Hindi maintains a stable second position throughout the decade. Its share increased from 14.75% in 2016 to 16.35% in 2021, before reaching at 15.91% in 2025. A national-level demand within the Indian market can be seen.

Within the major regional languages, Tamil showed notable swings. Its share declined from 4.24% in 2016 to 2.58% in 2020, recovered to 4.09% in 2022, and settled at 3.06% in 2025.

Bengali followed a stable upward direction, rising from 2.10% in 2016 to 3.74% in 2021, before adjusting to 3.21% by 2025. On the other way, Marathi showed a decline in share from 3.31% in 2016 to 2.17% in 2025.

Overall, all major languages have shown a sharp increase after 2020. English and Hindi continue to dominate, while regional languages remain underrepresented. This pattern highlights a multilingual publishing ecosystem in India.

Figure 4: Linguistic Composition of Indian Publishing (2016-2025)
Percentage Share of Major Languages

4.5 Language diversity

The year-wise language diversity in Indian Publications, measured by the Shannon Diversity Index from 2016 to 2025, reveals a period of increasing linguistic variety followed by a recent trend toward consolidation (Figure 5). The index shows a stable surge from 1.37 in 2016 to 1.45 in 2018, which indicates a growth of linguistic representation. From 2019 (1.45) to 2020 (1.50) and 2021 (1.52) the upward trend continued. Language diversity reached peak in 2022 with a Shannon Index value of 1.53. Subsequently, the index declined to 1.42 in 2023 and 1.41 in 2024, followed by a further decrease to 1.32 by 2025. This post-2022 contraction indicates that while the total volume of books is growing, publications are increasingly concentrating within a smaller number of dominant languages.

Figure 5: Language Diversity in Indian Publishing

4.6 Rating of the published books

The distribution of ISBNs by average rating highlights an uneven pattern, with a large proportion of publications lacks user ratings (Table 5). Out of a total of 423,269 ISBNs analyzed, the majority (264,508) fall into the zero-rating category which indicates that a large number of titles have not yet received any reader feedback or reviews.

Among the rated publications, books which received average ratings between 3.00 and 3.99 represent the largest share (73,944 ISBNs) which suggests that most evaluated titles receive moderate to good reader reception. This is followed by the 4.00 to 4.99 rating category, comprising 57,870 ISBNs which reflects a significant presence of highly rated publications. Titles with a perfect average rating of 5.00 account for 18,390 ISBNs that indicates a smaller yet notable segment of well received works.

In short, fewer ISBNs fall within the lower rating ranges. Publications with average ratings between 2.00 and 2.99 of total 6,676. Those in the 1.00 to 1.99 category are the least represented, with only 1,881 ISBNs. Overall, the rating distribution shows that books that receive ratings tend to cluster in the mid-to-high rating ranges. In contrast a dominant proportion of ISBNs remain unrated.

Table 5: Rating received from Goodreads

Average Rating	Number of ISBN
5	18390
4 to 4.99	57870
3 to 3.99	73944
2 to 2.99	6676
1 to 1.99	1881
0	264508
Total	423269

During the phase from 2016 to 2018 engagement levels showed stability. The annual number of rated books fluctuated within a consistent range from 8,092 in 2018 to 9,682 in 2017. A fluctuation was seen between 2019 and 2020; the publishing landscape entered into an expansion phase. Starting in 2021, there was a dramatic surge in reader interaction, with the number of titles receiving ratings escalating from 11,660 in 2021 to a significant peak of 30,108 in 2023. This rapid boost of reader engagement closely mirrors the quantitative expansion in ISBN issuances identified in previous sections that suggest a parallel growth in both production and active consumption.

In the final years of the study from 2024 to 2025, the data reflects a dwindling in engagement. The count of rated books adjusted from its 2023 peak to 24,608 in 2024 and 17,456 in 2025. Despite this recent decline, engagement levels at the close of the study period remain higher than the baseline during the early years. This can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Number of books with Goodreads Ratings (2016-2025)

4.7 Trends in e-book Production

The evolution of product forms within the Indian publishing industry reveals acute shift toward digital mediums. An analysis of ISBN-based publication data between 2016 and 2025 demonstrate a transition from digital presence to a dominant market pillar.

4.7.1 The Pre-Pandemic Baseline (2016-2019)

During the initial years of the study, the adoptions of the e-book format were in a beginning state. From 2016 to 2018, annual digital publications were very low that increased from 15 to 38 titles. By 2019, though there is a slight increase to 81 publications which represents an insignificant portion of the total ISBN output. It suggests the industry remained secured to traditional print-first methodologies.

4.7.2 The 2020 Inflection Point

The year 2020 marked a definitive revolutionary change in the industry's structural composition. The volume of e-book publications experienced an extraordinary surge increasing from 81 titles in 2019 to 4,171 in 2020. This inflection point signifies more than a temporary adaptation to the pandemic. It represents the formal "digital awakening" of the Indian publishing ecosystem.

4.7.3 Post-Pandemic Acceleration and Market Consolidation (2021-2025)

The digital direction moved to a sustained growth state following the 2020 surge. In 2021, the volume nearly tripled to 11,420 titles, stabilizing in 2022 (11,788) before taking a vertical ascent. By the latter half of the decade, the growth became significantly with 18,066 titles in 2023, 23,023 in 2024. It reached a peak of 37,308 publications by 2025 that is mentioned in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Number of total e-books published during 2016-2025

Overall, the findings suggest that Indian publishing experienced increasing language diversity up to the early post-pandemic period later shift toward linguistic consolidation was seen. This pattern shows the dynamic nature of language representation of the publishing trend in India.

5. Conclusion

This study shows that ISBN registration data serves as a bibliometric source for analysing national-level trends in book and printable media publishing in India. The analysis of ISBN data from 2016 to 2025 reveals a considerable growth in publishing activity and a temporary decline during the COVID-19 pandemic. Post-pandemic recovery can be seen also. This recovery phase is marked not only by a sharp rise in the volume of publications but also structural changes in language representation and product formats.

The findings clearly indicate a dominance of English-language in publishing which are nearly two-thirds of all ISBN registrations during the study period. The second most prominent language is Hindi. The regional languages like Tamil, Bengali, Marathi and Malayalam show steady growth and their representation remains limited. The Shannon Diversity Index highlighted the imbalance that linguistic diversity increased up to 2022. But a noticeable decline can be seen as publishing activity focuses in a few dominant languages. This trend shows a gradual integration of multilingual publishing ecosystem instead of balanced expansion.

This study also highlights reader engagement pattern using Goodreads ratings that a large proportion of publications remain unrated. Though publication output has expanded rapidly but visibility and reader interaction are distributed unevenly. The analysis of product forms uncovers a pivotal change toward digital publishing. e-book production risen distinctly from 2020 onward and continued after the pandemic. It highlights a long-term shift in the Indian publishing industry toward digital and online publicity.

The results highlight the need of introducing a policy that can support regional languages. The results give valuable insights for multilingual Collection Development, planning in national bibliography, and inclusive access strategy for libraries. Linguistic diversity along with digital growth is essential to ensure equitable knowledge dissemination. Further research may be continued by including subject-wise classification, regional publishing patterns and readership behaviour to understand India's emerging publishing scenario.

While the overall volume of ISBN registrations shows robust growth, the data reveals a trend toward linguistic consolidation, where an increase in output is paired with a measurable decline in linguistic diversity. This shift underscores the need for targeted policies to support regional languages that may be losing ground despite the expanding publishing market.

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Annexure I :Data format collected from the ISBN portal

Book Title	ISBN	Product Form	Language	Applicant Type	Name of Publishing Agency/Publisher	Name of Author/Editor	Publication Date
ISC Modern English Literature Skills Poetry Reflections Class XI	978-93-6963-495-8	Paperback / softback	English	Publisher	Goyal Brothers Prakashan	Editor: M. Aggarwal	28-02-2025
ISC Modern English Literature Skills Drama Pygmalion Class XI	978-93-6963-191-9	Paperback / softback	English	Publisher	Goyal Brothers Prakashan	Editor: M. Aggarwal	28-02-2025

ISC Modern English Literature Skills Prose Perspective Class XI	978-93- 6963-042-4	Paperback / softback	Engli sh	Publisher	Goyal Brothers Prakashan	Editor: M. Aggarwal	28-02- 2025
BOT-152 : Practical Botany	978-93- 49325-23-4	Book	Engli sh	Publisher	Prashant Publications	Author: Dr. B. A. Patil, Dr. D. M. Mahajan, Dr. Asha B. Kadam, Dr. S. R. Kale, Dr. S. M. Kamble	28-02- 2025
मेरे अंतर्मन की वेदनाएँ: मेरी कविताएँ	978-93- 6355-995-0	Paperback / softback	Hindi	Publisher	Evincepub Publishing	Author: कु मारीवि	28-02- 2025
Godfrey Morgan A Californian Mystery	978-93- 6995-336-3	Paperback / softback	Engli sh	Publisher	Tarang Prakashan	Author: Jules Verne	28-02- 2025